

The UK Quality and Outcomes Framework (QOF) was introduced in 2004, and meant that about one fifth of general practitioners' (GPs) income depended on their performance measured by 150 quality indicators. QOF cost hundreds of millions of pounds per year, and imposed considerable work on GPs.

In this paper, we summarised all previous research examining the impact of QOF payments to GPs for achieving quality targets.

What happens when the NHS...	Impact at one year	Impact at three years
<p>Introduced payment for achieving quality targets?</p> <p>83 different quality measures examined</p>	<p>Quality improves for most measures</p> <p>Average improvement in quality is only small</p>	
<p>Withdrew payment for achieving quality targets?</p> <p>31 different quality measures examined</p>	<p>Quality gets worse for almost all measures</p> <p>Average reduction in quality is persistent</p>	

Conclusion: paying UK GPs to achieve quality targets did not lead to lasting improvements in quality. Other ways of improvement quality like education, data feedback, and support to reorganise care may be better.

Read more in the full paper at <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-083424>

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH

